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MACHINE LEARNING-BASED MODELLING FOR NUMERICAL EVALUATION OF THE TRAFFIC SPEED DEFLECTOMETER PERFORMANCE

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INTRODUCTION

A Traffic Speed Deflectometer (TSD) has become increasingly popular in recent years as a tool for measuring the structural condition of pavements [1]. Unlike the Falling Weight Deflectometer (FWD), TSD (figure 1: left and right) does not require traffic control during the measurement process. This allows measurements to be taken under actual traffic conditions, providing more accurate data that can be used to identify variations in pavement conditions [2].

TSD is a relatively new continuous deflection device. Whenever a new device is introduced, it is imperative to compare it with the existing measurement devices to evaluate the extent to which the new device can replace the old one. Therefore, the verification of TSD measurements of in-service roads is of great importance before their widespread implementation in Pavement Management System (PMS) activities [3]. However, the traditional method for verifying TSD measurements is destructive testing, which involves excavating a section of pavement and measuring the response of the underlying layers using sensors, geophones, and accelerometers. Even though the significance of the destructive method is associated with an accurate and reliable performance, it could lead to relatively significant destructive damage on the pavement during the inspection, and it is high time and cost-consuming. In this context, relevant research reveals the necessity of a new approach that is more adequate to address the issue [1, 2].

To this extent, Machine Learning (ML) has emerged as a promising approach in the pavement-engineering ecosystem. It enables the automatic analysis of large data sets and the detection of complex patterns, leading to improved efficiency compared to traditional methods [4].

The aim of this paper is to explore the possibility of using a machine learning-based approach to achieve an effective backcalculation of the resilient modulus. The study aims to investigate the hypothesis that machine learning techniques can be utilized to accurately estimate the resilient modulus, which is a critical parameter in pavement engineering. By examining the feasibility of using machine learning algorithms in pavement engineering applications, this research aims to contribute to the development of more efficient and accurate methods for estimating pavement material properties.

Therefore, this paper aims to investigate the hypothesis that a reliable non-destructive technique for TSD measurement verification can be achieved through a machine learning-based approach. The objective of the proposed ML approach is to increase the accuracy of TSD measurements while reducing operating costs and minimizing the environmental impact associated with traditional destructive testing methods.

The methodology of this approach involves a multi-step process. Firstly, a literature review has been conducted to examine the relationship between Traffic Speed Deflectometer (TSD) and Falling Weight Deflectometer (FWD). It then explores the destructive method for TSD

measurement verification before introducing the machine learning model used in the study, Support Vector Regression (SVR).

Secondly, a numerical modelling has been developed, which involves constructing an analytical database and simulating the TSD and FWD deflection bowl. Data processing is also included in this part of the methodology. The analytical model used is based on Burmester's elastic linear isotropic approach with infinite in-plane layers [5].

Thirdly, machine learning techniques are applied to analyze and predict deflection values based on collected data. The process begins with training of SVR model using a Gaussian kernel on a portion of the database designated as training data.

The performance of the model is evaluated using the remaining portion of the database designated as testing data. The SVR model's parameters, are optimized using a grid search method to enhance its performance. Finally, the optimized SVR model is used to predict the simulated deflection from FWD based on TSD simulated measurement data. [6].

To validate the performance of the proposed procedure, the predicted FWD measurements were compared to the simulated one. The comparison was based on several statistical metrics, such as Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and coefficient of determination (R^2).

Figure 1: Measurement Principle of FWD (left) and TSD (right)

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1. THE CORRELATION BETWEEN TSD AND FWD

The relationship between TSD and FWD measurements in pavement engineering is an area of ongoing research. TSD and FWD are used to measure pavement deflection and evaluate structural integrity; however, they have different measurement methods [1].

FWD is a more accurate and cost-effective project-level method that uses a known load. The device drops a weight onto the tested surface, causing deformation or "deflection." The resulting deformation is then used to calculate the structural characteristics of the surface [2].

On the other hand, TSD measures pavement deflection velocity instead of measuring vertical deflections caused by the truck's rear axle. TSD measurements are taken over a specific distance interval, such as 1-10 meters, mainly to reduce the impact of noise. The vertical deflections are then calculated from these measurements, and a curve is fitted between the slope deflections and the offsets. One of the main benefits of TSD over the FWD is its ability to conduct measurements without traffic control. Additionally, TSD provides more detailed large datasets that can be used to identify variations in pavement conditions [1-3].

Figure (2) shows one of the correlation studies that conducted by Katicha et al. Although this study has shown a correlation between TSD and FWD measurements, however, further research is needed to understand this relationship in a more comprehensive manner.

Figure 2: TSD d₀ and FWD d₀ measurements on section UK_F1 Source (3)

1.2 THE DESTRUCTIVE METHOD FOR THE VERIFICATION OF TSD MEASUREMENTS

The method for verifying TSD measurements currently in use is destructive testing. In this method (figure 3), sensors, geophones, and accelerometers are placed in the pavement before testing to compare TSD measurements with the actual properties of the pavement structure obtained by removing a small portion of the pavement. The advantages of this method include the ability to directly compare TSD measurements with the actual properties of the pavement structure. Still, it is also costly and time-consuming, as well as causing damage to the pavement surface. Additionally, it only provides data for a limited number of locations and may need to provide a complete understanding of the pavement condition [1, 8, 9].

Figure 3: Annotated photograph of the testing site located on Leach Highway, near Shelley WA, Shelley, Western Australia. Source [9]

1.3 SUPPORT VECTOR REGRESSION (SVR)

Support Vector Regression (SVR) is a supervised machine learning technique that models the relationship between input variables (independent variables) and output variables (dependent variables). It is especially useful for data that is not linearly separable. One of SVR's strengths is its ability to employ kernel functions, such as the Gaussian kernel, to transform input variables into a higher dimensional space. This enhances the precision of predictions, making it ideal for use in pavement engineering, where the data is often complex and non-linear. SVR provides an effective solution for modeling non-linear relationships between input and output variables. [6].

In a one-dimensional illustration of SVR, the data points show the predicted values, as demonstrated in (figure 4). Meanwhile, the line displays the actual or reference values. The two dotted lines outline the boundaries that are set at a distance, ξ , from the reference data [7].

- (\mathbf{w}) a learned weight vectors
- (b) Measurement baise
- (\mathbf{X}_i) the i -th training instance
- (\mathbf{y}_i) the training label
- (ξ_i) the distance between the bounds and predicted values that fall outside bounds.

Figure 4: Illustrating the one-dimensional SVR model. Source [7]

In SVR, two parameters control the model's complexity and performance. The first one is called C . It is a regularization parameter controlling the trade-off between accuracy and margin of the hyperplane. Whereas the second one is named Γ . It controls the width of the Radial Based Function (RBF) kernel, which holds the degree of non-linearity of the model. The optimal values are determined through hyper-parameter tuning, which involves training the model with different combinations of C and Γ values and evaluating their performance using a validation set [6, 7]. After analyzing the SVR results and comparing them with other findings presented in [12], it can be concluded that SVR exhibits exceptional performance.

2. ANALYTICAL DATABASE

2.1. NUMERICAL MODEL

A numerical database of pavement structures has been created. This database includes a variety of pavement structures with varying thicknesses and material properties, some of which are partially or fully damaged. The database also considers environmental conditions by incorporating different vertical temperature profiles in the pavement layers.

The simulation of the synthetic database was done using the software Alizé2® [10]. It is software that has been a vital tool in designing French motorways for more than 30 years. Using a multi-layer elastic linear model, it utilizes Burmister's model to calculate the resilient stresses, strains, and deflections.

Alizé2® also allows for comparing calculated values to admissible ones, which can be determined based on the fatigue characteristics of the materials or the rutting behaviors under specified traffic levels. The software also includes a database of material properties based on the French standard guide and catalog [5, 10].

After the development of the data-frame was chosen for further analysis. The characteristics of this data frame that represents the pavement sections used in the current study are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Characteristics of the Pavement Sections used in the current study

Layer	Thickness h (m)	Material (M)	Modulus E (MPa)	Nu	Interface	°C
1	0.06	eb-bbsg3*	7000	0.35	(1) bound	15
2	0.09	gb2**	9300		(1) bound	
3	0.09	gb2**	9300		(1) bound	
4	Infinity	Pf4***	16-230		(0) non-bound	

* **eb-bbsg3**: asphalt mix, class 3 semi-grained aggregate bituminous concrete.

** **gb3**: class 3 aggregate bituminous concrete.

*** **pf4**: class 4 subgrade.

2.1.1 NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF TSD & FWD DEFLECTION BOWL

The numerical simulation of deflection behavior under FWD and TSD involves creating a mathematical model of the pavement structure and applying load to the model to predict how the pavement will respond to FWD and TSD testing. This simulation considers the various parameters that can affect pavement deflection, such as the material properties of the pavement layers, the load applied by the device, and the temperature, as well as the mechanical condition of the pavement structure at the time of testing .

Overall, the deflection readings from an FWD and the calculated deflection from a single-wheel TSD are not directly equivalent. FWD measures pavement deflection, while TSD measures pavement deflection velocity. In other words, both devices account for pavement deflection but with different characteristics, such as load configurations and measurement techniques.

Thus, the deflection recorded from both tests needs to be normalized to obtain equivalent values. The normalization process involves converting the deflection readings to an analogous elastic layer deflection using a loading transfer function, which considers the differences in load configuration and loading method between the two tests. This process assumes that both tests are simulated on the same pavement section and that the simulated measurements are taken at the same temperature and pavement conditions .

Consequently, FWD and TSD data can be processed with various software programs to produce visual representations of the deflection and structural information. Thus, the simulation process of the deflection behavior under FWD starts by determining the deflection caused by a single TSD wheel at various distances from the loading points.

The Alizé2® software is used to accomplish this step after the material properties and TSD configuration have been established. In the next step, the deflection caused by each wheel of the TSD is determined separately through interpolation.

To this end, the simulation of deflection behavior under TSD involves the following four steps:

- The first step is calculating the deflection under a reference single TSD wheel almost equivalent to the FWD. Given the defined material properties and TSD configuration, this can be achieved as a function of the distance to the loading points using Alizé2® software.
- The second step involves independently interpolating the deflection under each of the TSD's ten wheels.
- The third step applies the principle of load superposition to determine the deflection under the sum of the wheels, as seen in the red curve of Figure 5a.
- The fourth and final step calculates the deflection under TSD by analytically integrating the velocity curve in figure 5b, which is the black curve in Figure 5a.

It is crucial to note that the discrepancy between the actual deflection velocity and the measured simulated one in (figure 5b) arises from the assumption that there is negligible deflection velocity recorded at the rear axle wheel (loading point). Similarly, there is also negligible deflection velocity recorded position of the reference Doppler laser sensor. However, the lack of deflection velocity recorded at the loading point and the location of the reference sensor can influence the accuracy of the simulated deflection velocity and increase measurement uncertainty.

Ultimately, it is worth to mention that, the data frame is a specific type of database that is commonly used in case studies and research methodology, as it allows for efficient organization and manipulation of large datasets for analysis.

Figure 5 – (a) Simulation of TSD Deflection

Figure 5 – (b) Real to calculated deflection velocity

2.1.2 DATA PROCESSING

This part of the study aimed to determine the relationship between TSD and FWD maximum deflection. To do so, a dataset consisting of 110 cases of simulated TSD and FWD deflection has been analyzed, as shown in figure 6. Furthermore, figure 7 (a and b) displays the maximum deflection data obtained from varying the soil modulus E4 for both TSD and FWD deflection.

TSD maximum deflection was between 180 to 1,300 μm and FWD deflection between 110 to 640 μm . The soil modulus E4 was gradually reduced from 230 to 16 MPa.

The data showed a uniform pattern in the maximum D0 deflection and higher TSD deflection compared to FWD. This implies the significance of FWD in evaluating TSD performance in road pavement conditions inspection.

Figure 6 – Relationship between TSD1 and FWD1 maximum deflection

Figure 7 – (a) Maximum TSD Deflection Range (b) Maximum FWD Deflection Range

2.2 TRAINING OF SVR MODEL

Figure (8) illustrates the process of training and evaluating the SVR algorithm. The data is first divided into 70% for training and 30% for testing.

The purpose of dividing the data into two parts is to avoid overfitting, which occurs when a model is too closely fit to the training data and performs poorly on unseen data. Using a separate testing dataset makes it possible to see how well the model generalizes to new data.

The training data fits the SVR model and allows it to learn the patterns. The model is then evaluated on the testing data, to assess its performance.

The learning process involves finding the optimal parameters for the SVR model so that it can make accurate predictions on unseen data.

Figure 8 – FWD data split 70% training and 30% testing

2.3 TESTING OF THE SVR MODEL

The correlation between predicted and simulated FWD deflections is shown in figure 9(a & b). The comparison was made using a statistical model, specifically the SVR algorithm. The model's performance was evaluated using the R^2 metric, which measures the model's goodness of fit to the data. The results showed that the model had a high R^2 value of 0.998, indicating a good fit. The slope and intercept of the model were close to unity and zero, respectively. Additionally, the residuals between the predicted and simulated measurements had no systematic trend and a high Pearson correlation of 0.999, with a maximum variance of $15 \mu\text{m}$ out of the range of $[100 - 600] \mu\text{m}$. Finally, the ability of the model to produce the same population as the simulated FWD was tested at a 95% significance level.

Figure 9(a) The correlation between predicted and simulated FWD deflections

Figure 9(b) The variance between predicted and simulated FWD deflections

2.3 HYPERPARAMETER TUNING

As stated previously, C and Gamma are essential parameters controlling the model's complexity and performance.

In this study, a grid search is a method used in machine learning to find the best set of hyperparameters for a model. The grid search was performed on an SVR model to determine the best combination of parameters.

As shown in (figure 10), the grid search tried 128 combinations of these parameters and fit the SVR model 5 times for each variety, resulting in 640 fits. The best combination of parameters was found to be C=10000.0, kernel=RBF, and gamma=0.071, with a score of 0.997.

The score is a measure of the performance of the average model, and a higher score indicates a better fit. In this case, the best parameters resulted in a score of 0.997, meaning that the SVM model with these hyperparameters had a 99.7% accuracy in fitting the data.

Figure 10: Hyperparameters grid search for tuning SVR's C & Gamma

3. CONCLUSION & PERSPECTIVE

3.1. CONCLUSION

This study presents a practical and reliable procedure for verifying TSD-simulated measurements at the network level. The process uses FWD-simulated measurements as the basis for verification, providing a quick and straightforward method. The SVR model converts the measured TSD deflections to the corresponding FWD deflections. The SVR model was trained and tested using numerical data from the Alizé2® program. Results showed that the model could accurately predict FWD deflections with high R^2 values and low RMSE. In summary, using FWD-simulated measurements and SVRs facilitates the verification of TSD deflections, allowing highway agencies to adopt the proposed procedure with limited FWD testing. Moreover, this approach offers several advantages over traditional methods, such as increased accuracy and efficiency and the ability to handle large amounts of data. Furthermore, the use of machine learning models might allow the integration of additional factors, such as weather conditions and traffic volume, which can further improve the accuracy of the TSD measurements. However, it is crucial to ensure that the machine learning models are adequately trained and validated using a representative and high-quality dataset. Additionally, it is essential to consider the models' limitations and regularly update them to account for changes in the road network and traffic conditions. It is also worth noting that the proposed procedure has some limitations and uncertainties, such as the effect of the measurement conditions, such as the temperature and surface condition, the vehicle speed, etc., on the TSD measurements. Additionally, the proposed procedure assumes that the behavior of the pavement structure model is elastic linear, and homogenous, which may only sometimes be the case. Therefore, further research is needed to validate the proposed procedure under different conditions and investigate the method's potential limitations and uncertainties. The results of the study suggest that incorporating the proposed model into current Traffic Speed Deflectometer calibration and measurement interpretation could enhance road conditions and minimize maintenance expenses. However, it is important to acknowledge that the study has limitations, such as the use of synthetic data that may not precisely reflect real-world conditions. Therefore, further evaluations using controlled and uncontrolled experimental data are necessary to verify the model's effectiveness under actual field conditions. The paper also highlights the possibility of using other machine learning models to optimize the proposed approach's performance and expand its application to other areas of pavement engineering. Overall, the proposed approach has significant potential to revolutionize subgrade evaluation and pave the way for improved road infrastructure.

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